

ISOTHERMS, DIFFERENTIAL HEATS, ENTROPY, AND
THERMOKINETICS OF META-XYLENE ADSORPTION IN BAY
ZEOLITE

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Abstract

This study explores the adsorption isotherms, differential heats (Q_d), entropy changes (ΔS_d), and adsorption kinetics (τ) of meta-xylene on BaY zeolite at 303 K. Experimental data were analyzed and compared with the theoretical framework of the Theory of Volume Filling of Micropores (TVFM). The adsorption isotherms are satisfactorily described using a three-term TVFM equation. The differential heats and entropy changes exhibit complex wave-like behavior, reflecting different mechanisms of interaction between meta-xylene and Ba cations at various crystallographic sites. The kinetics revealed a delayed equilibrium time, influenced by the energy distribution of adsorption sites. The results highlight the thermodynamic and kinetic complexity of meta-xylene adsorption in BaY zeolite.

1. Introduction

Zeolites, a class of crystalline porous materials, exhibit molecular-scale porosity (<2 nm) and are widely applied in industrial processes due to their selective adsorption and catalytic properties [1-3]. They are constructed from TO_4 tetrahedra (T = Si, Al, or P) linked via oxygen atoms into three-dimensional frameworks [4-5]. Among synthetic zeolites, BaY is particularly significant for separating xylene isomers and removing sulfur compounds from hydrocarbons [6]. Despite advancements in zeolite research, the thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of meta-xylene adsorption on BaY remain underexplored.

2. Experimental Methods

1. **Materials:**

- BaY zeolite activated at 400° C for 4 hours to remove moisture and other adsorbed impurities.
- Meta-xylene with a purity of 99.9%.

2. **Methods:**

- Adsorption isotherms were measured using a static method at 303 K.
- Differential heats (Q_d) were calculated based on calorimetric data.
- Entropy changes (ΔS_d) were determined using the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation.
- Kinetics of adsorption were analyzed by monitoring equilibrium times (τ) at different adsorption capacities.

3. **Equations:**

- **Adsorption isotherm:**

$$a=0,829\exp[-(A/10,79)^2]+0,1556\exp[-(A/8,58)^3]+0,128\exp[-(A/1,57)^3]$$

where a is the adsorption (mol/g), and $A=RT\ln(P^0/P)$ is the adsorption work.

- **Entropy changes:** $\Delta S_d = - (Q_d - \Delta_v H) / T - R \ln (p/p^0)$
- **Kinetics:** Equilibrium time (τ) was determined based on adsorption rates at various capacities.

3. **Results and Discussion**

1. **Adsorption Isotherms:** Experimental data matched well with the three-term TVFM model ($R^2=0.972$). At low adsorption ($a < 0.87$ mmol/g), the isotherm exhibited a concave shape, transitioning into a sharp rise at $a=1.11$ mmol/g. The theoretical and experimental isotherms are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Adsorption isotherms of meta-xylene in BaY zeolite.

2. **Differential Heats (dQd):** dQd varied between 292.27 kJ/mol and 39.0 kJ/mol, with an initial peak corresponding to adsorption on BaIII' sites. Subsequent fluctuations reflect adsorption on BaII cations, transitioning to condensation effects in micropores (Figure 2) [9-10] .

Figure 2. Differential heat of adsorption as a function of adsorption.

- Entropy (ΔS_d):** Entropy changes indicated a highly constrained state of meta-xylene molecules in the zeolite framework. The entropy rose from $-600 \text{ J/mol}\cdot\text{K}$ at low a to $-180 \text{ J/mol}\cdot\text{K}$, followed by a decline (Figure 3). This suggests molecular migration within the zeolite structure [11-12] .

Figure 3. Adsorption entropy of meta-xylene in BaY zeolite.

4. **Kinetics:** Equilibrium times (τ) ranged from 12 hours for low adsorption to 2 hours at higher capacities. This reflects the transition from adsorption on BaIII' sites to filling of micropores (Figure 4) [13] .

5.

Figure 4. Equilibrium time as a function of adsorption capacity.

4. Conclusion

Meta-xylene adsorption on BaY zeolite is characterized by complex thermodynamic and kinetic behaviors. Differential heats reveal multiple adsorption mechanisms involving BaIII' and BaII cations, while entropy changes highlight constrained molecular states. The TVFM model effectively describes the adsorption isotherm, offering insights into the interactions of meta-xylene with zeolite frameworks.

References

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